

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“AWAKENING AMBITION”

'The reason everyone goes into education is to have a powerful influence on the educational lives of students.' A quote that I read and became my motivation while I am still in college studying Bachelor in Elementary Education. I wanted to make a difference in my future young learners in the future which I did when I am unexpectedly called to join the DepEd family in the year 2020. At first, I gave my best since it's my first year. "Puyat" is real. They said I will make Learning Modules for the learners, without hesitation and training. I did make my first Learning Material which my name was written as a developer. I was surprised that I even made 4 Self-Learning Modules during the pandemic. I lose weight but losing it gives tiresome but a satisfaction that I really did give my best. During that time, I made these accomplishments because the school leader that time didn't give me so much other task.

But years goes by then I am experiencing burn out because of so may added others task not relating to teaching. So sometimes I asked myself "Am I still making difference?" But then to change my routine I decided to enrolled. It was tough at first like doing your job and studying as well. I realize in an optimal position to have an affect great change and provide for the larger "good." I want to make a difference in administration.

I observed also that some of the school leaders use this title to easily manipulate teachers who can easily say degrading words. Words implying that we teachers can easily replace and in teachers hiring has a long line that is waiting for you to quit.

Even just getting supplies, it seems like they are doing it hard for you to request for your needed supplies. The relationship also is like have a huge gap within. I cannot say my ideas and suggestions freely. That is the reason why I felt like I was not also heard. Some my colleagues also these sentiments even if they have long years experienced.

In my district, there are different behaviors shown by the school leaders. Some are very hands-on in doing school-activities, tough in implying policies, motherly figure but some gives and asked orders while you on leave.

After learning all the topics discussed during the School Organization, Administration and Supervision I was eager to learn more and do more. I never dreamed of becoming one of the school leader but I knew administrative role would give me the opportunity to possibly do the most good for my learners and my colleagues. I was not only intrigued but inspired to implement the kind of supervision promulgated by the lesson I learned. I am dreaming now of me having the opportunity to employ some of that which I had learned. Supervision was a process in which I'd engage with them as co-partners to improve teaching, not through dogmatic or inspectional practices, but via a differentiated approach to supervision that encouraged

them to think deeply about their teaching. I am dreaming now to serve as "another set of eyes" to share thoughts about their teaching in a conversational, non-evaluative, and unobtrusive manner. Ultimately, I would love to apply soon and say, it was essentially concerned with encouraging their thought and commitment to improving teaching.

Hence, once a losing motivation now a dreamer who wanted to make difference not just my learner but as a school even with my colleagues. I hope I would be given a chance to be more inspired in performing my roles and exhibits leadership. From the report I have learned, that administration has to do with setting up rule and policies, making plans for those who are in lower position to execute. But for now, to attained common goal, I'll do my best to work hand and hand together as discussed in this lesson that we need also to do our part not blaming others. I may have different roles and functions but we all have a common goal. I am hoping that nobody will be treated less just because I fall under lower. Once having passion fatigue now a dreamer big or small because no matter what you do it with passion and honestly then I matter because one way or another I have contributed to the success of the organization.

